

Synthesis and spectroscopic characterization of bromodioxotriphenylphosphine oxide (*N,N'*-dialkyldithiocarbamate/*O*-alkyldithiocarbonate)molybdenum(VI) complexes and the crystal structure of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide

John E. Drake^a, Michael B. Hursthouse^b, Ravindra Kumar^c, Mark E. Light^b, Raju Ratnani^{c*} and Keerti Saraswat^c

^aDepartment of Chemistry and Biochemistry, University of Windsor, Windsor, Ontario, N9B 3P4, Canada

^bDepartment of Chemistry, University of Southampton, Highfield, Southampton, SO17 1BJ, UK

^cDepartment of Pure and Applied Chemistry, M. D. S. University, Ajmer-305 009, Rajasthan, India

E-mail : ratnaniraju@rediffmail.com

Manuscript received 10 March 2008, accepted 4 June 2008

Abstract : A new series of bromodioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, MoO₂Br(S₂CNR₂)(OPPh₃) (NR₂ = NEt₂, N(*i*-Pr)₂, NCH₂(CH₂)₃CH₂) and MoO₂Br(S₂COR)(OPPh₃) (R = Et, *n*-Pr, *i*-Pr) were prepared by the reaction of dibromodioxobis(triphenylphosphineoxide)molybdenum(VI) with sodium/potassium salts of the corresponding dithiocarbamates or dithiocarbonates in 1 : 1 molar ratio in dichloromethane. These newly synthesized complexes were characterized on the basis of elements analysis and spectral (IR and ¹H NMR) studies. The crystal structure of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide is also described. [CMeCHCHCMeCHNH]Br crystallizes as monoclinic in the space group P2₁/c with cell parameters *a* = 8.6591(9), *b* = 13.252(1), *c* = 7.258(1) Å, β = 101.94(1)°, *V* = 814.9(2) Å³, *Z* = 4, *R* = 0.0393, *R*_w = 0.0885.

Keywords : Molybdenum, dithiocarbamate, dithiocarbonate, triphenylphosphineoxide, 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide.

Introduction

The coordination chemistry of Mo^V and Mo^{VI} has remained an interesting field of research for chemists in view of its significant role in a number of important enzymatic systems¹⁻³ in which molybdenum is believed to be associated with flavins and aminoacid residues. The exact nature of these interactions is not understood and a number of model studies have been carried out to characterize further the coordination chemistry of molybdenum⁴⁻⁷. In contrast to other metals which are active in biological systems, the oxidation states of molybdenum in these systems are generally high, usually +5 or +6. Crystal structures and model studies of molybdoenzymes on MoO₂X₂·2L (X = Cl, Br; L = OPPh₃, DMSO)⁸⁻¹¹ have been reported. Dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes are useful precursors¹¹ for the synthesis of other molybdenum complexes via oxygen or chlorine abstraction or substitution^{12,13}. They are also potential catalysts in oxotransfer reactions^{14,15}.

Complexes of molybdenum with bidentate sulphur

donor ligands such as dithiocarbamates, dithiocarbonates and dithiophosphates have been reported extensively by Steifel *et al.*¹⁶. The interest in the chemistry of these systems arises in part from the involvement of molybdenum associated with sulphur ligands in the redox-active molybdoenzymes^{16,17}.

In the recent past we have successfully prepared and reported a series of chlorodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide-(*O,O*-dialkyl/diphenyl(alkylene)dithiophosphate)molybdenum(VI) complexes⁹. We were interested in checking the stability of their bromo analogs with other dithio ligands viz. dithiocarbamates and dithiocarbonates. We were also interested in growing suitable crystals for single crystal X-ray structure determination but our efforts went in vain. In this paper, we describe the reactions of dibromodioxobis(triphenylphosphineoxide)molybdenum(VI) with sodium or potassium salts of *N,N*-dialkyldithiocarbamate or *O*-alkyldithiocarbonate to yield complexes such as MoO₂Br(S₂CNR₂)(OPPh₃) and MoO₂Br(S₂COR)(OPPh₃) along with their characterization by various spectroscopic techniques. The crystal structure of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide is described.

Results and discussion

The complexes $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{L})(\text{OPPh}_3)$ ($\text{L} = \text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2$ or S_2COR) have been obtained as yellow solids in good yields from the reaction of dibromodioxobis(triphenylphosphine-oxide)molybdenum(VI) complexes suspended in CH_2Cl_2 with one mole equivalent of the corresponding sodium/potassium salt of N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamate or O -alkyldithiocarbonate in dichloromethane.

The liberated NaBr was separated by filtration, volatile components of the filtrate were removed by evaporation under reduced pressure and free OPPh_3 (non-volatile) was removed by repeatedly washing the solid products with hexane. These molybdenum(VI) complexes are yellow powdery solids that are soluble in chloroform and dichloromethane and are characterized by microanalysis, IR and ^1H NMR spectroscopy.

IR spectra :

The assignments of the IR bands for bromodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide(N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamate)molybdenum(VI) and bromodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide(O -alkyldithiocarbonate)molybdenum(VI) complexes (Table 1) were made by comparison with the spectra of the precursors, dibromodioxobis(triphenylphosphineoxide)molybdenum(VI)¹⁸ and the sodium/potassium salts of N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamates¹⁹ and O -alkyldithiocarbonates²⁰. The bands arising from the C-N stretching mode in the dithiocarbamate derivatives, **1-3**, are seen in the range

1485–1505 cm^{-1} typical of analogous complexes¹⁰. Similarly, the presence of a band around 1260–1265 cm^{-1} in the dithiocarbonate derivatives can be attributed to $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$ ^{10,21}. Complexes with both dithio ligand systems show CS_2 group stretching vibration bands in the range 995–1010 cm^{-1} suggesting bidentate attachment of the dithio ligands²².

A strong to medium band due to $\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$ in the complexes is observed in the range 1140–1150 cm^{-1} , at lower wave number than in free OPPh_3 (1189 cm^{-1}), which is indicative of coordination through the oxygen atom²³. Two characteristic strong bands in the range of 900–950 cm^{-1} can be assigned to the $(\text{Mo}=\text{O})$ symmetric and antisymmetric stretching modes²⁴ in dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes, **1-6**.

^1H NMR spectra :

The chemical shifts and integrated intensity ratios of the protons on the dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes are given in Table 2. These spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 solutions at room temperature. For dithiocarbamates and dithiocarbonates, the effect of coordination is to deshield the protons, presumably because of an increased contribution of the canonical forms ($\text{R}_2\text{N}^+ = \text{CS}_2^-$ and $\text{R}-\text{O}^+ = \text{CS}_2^-$). This suggests bonding of these dithio ligands to the molybdenum atom. The ^1H NMR data of dioxomolybdenum(VI) complexes are remarkably similar to those of the salts of dithiocarbamates and dithiocarbonates probably due to the large separation between the molybdenum and protons. The phenyl protons due to OPPh_3 show a downfield shift compared to the free ligand, which again confirms the coordination of the ligand.

Molecular structure of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide, $[\text{CMeCHCHCMeCHNH}]\text{Br}$:

In an attempt to prepare $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}_2(\text{CMeCHCHCMe}-$

Table 1. IR spectral data (cm^{-1}) of bromodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide (N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamates and O -alkyldithiocarbonates) molybdenum(VI) complexes^a

Sr. No.	Compd.	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ or $\nu(\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{P}-\text{C})$	$\nu(\text{P}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}=\text{S})$	$\nu(\text{Mo}=\text{O})$
1.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1505(s)	1435(s)	1140(s)	1000(m)	905(s), 950(s)
2.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNPr}^i_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1485(s)	1445(s)	1150(s)	1000(m)	900(s), 945(s)
3.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNC}_5\text{H}_{10})(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1485(s)	1440(s)	1150(s)	995(m)	900(s), 945(s)
4.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COEt})(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1265(m)	1440(s)	1140(m)	1005(m)	905(s), 950(s)
5.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COPr}^i)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1260(br)	1445(s)	1145(m)	1010(m)	900(s), 945(s)
6.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COPr}^i)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	1265(br)	1440(s)	1150(s)	1000(m)	905(s), 950(s)

^aKey : s = strong; m = medium; w = weak; br = broad.

Table 2. ^1H NMR spectral data of bromodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide (N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamates and O -alkyldithiocarbonates) molybdenum(VI) complexes^{a,b}

Sr. No.	Compd.	$\text{NCH}_2/\text{OCH}_2/ \text{NCH/OCH}$	$\text{NCCH}_3/\text{OCCH}_3 \text{NCCH}_2/\text{NCCCH}_2$	PPh_3
1.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	3.88 (4H, q)	1.42 (6H, t)	7.26–7.7 (15H, m)
2.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNPr}^i_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	3.55 (2H, m)	0.90 (6H, d)	7.26–7.70 (15H, m)
3.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNC}_5\text{H}_{10})(\text{OPPh}_3)$	4.02 (4H, m, <i>o</i> - CH_2)	3.85 (4H, m, <i>m</i> - CH_2) 1.85 (2H, m, <i>p</i> - CH_2)	7.46–7.70 (15H, m)
4.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COEt})(\text{OPPh}_3)$	3.78 (2H, q)	1.40 (3H, t)	7.45–7.52 (15H, m)
5.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COPr}^i)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	3.51 (2H, t)	1.70 (2H, m) 1.24 (3H, t)	7.20–7.70 (15H, m)
6.	$\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COPr}^i)(\text{OPPh}_3)$	3.68 (1H, m)	1.17 (6H, d)	7.20–7.70 (15H, m)

^aThe spectra were recorded in CDCl_3 and reported in δ ppm from MeSi. ^bNumber of protons and multiplicities are in parentheses (d = doublet; t = triplet; m = multiplet).

$\text{CHN})_2$, we fortuitously obtained X-ray quality crystals of $[\text{CMeCH}_2\text{CMeCHNH}]\text{Br}$ which crystallizes as monoclinic in the space group $P2_1/c$. The asymmetric unit is displayed as an ORTEP diagram in Fig. 1. The bond

Fig. 1. ORTEP plot of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide. The non-hydrogen atoms are drawn with 50% probability ellipsoids.

distances C1–C6 (1.500(5) Å) and C4–C7 (1.501(5) Å) are as expected for C–C single bonds whereas the remaining C–C distances correspond to aromatic C=C double bonds (aver. 1.387(5) Å), comparable to those reported for 2,5-dimethylpyridium 2,5-dichloro-6-hydroxy-1,4-benzoquinone-3-olate²⁵. The bromide ion forms a classical linear (179(4)°) N–H---Br hydrogen bond with H---Br and N---Br distances of 2.38(5) and 3.183(3) Å, respectively. There are no other close contacts with the bromide ion. By contrast, a novel framework of N–H---Br hydrogen bonds, in which the bromide ion is in an

approximately tetrahedral arrangement, results in the formation of Br(4,4')-bipyridinium supramolecular synthons with short H---Br distances (2.38–2.55 Å) and N–H---Br angles (140–155°)²⁶. In a study of histamine H_1 -receptors, all three bromide ions in $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{17}\text{BrN}_5\text{O}_3^+ \cdot \text{Br}^{3-}$ form two N–H---Br hydrogen bonds with angles in the range (153.1–173.4°) and H---Br and N---Br distances (2.24–2.50 and 3.198(4)–3.366(4) Å), respectively²⁷. Similar ranges of angles and distances are also found when the N–H---Br hydrogen bonds involve bromine that is bonded to a metal atom as exemplified by those in $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2][\text{CuBr}_3(\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{BrN}_2)]$ ²⁸ (N–H---Br angles 151–175°; H---Br 2.47–2.70 and N---Br distances 3.42(2)–3.64(2) Å) and in $[\text{C}_5\text{H}_7\text{N}_2]_2[\text{CuBr}_4]$ ²⁸ (N–H---Br angles 139(4)–175(5)°; H---Br 2.30(6)–2.58(6) and N---Br distances 3.31(1)–3.48(1) Å), where again all bromide ions are bridging.

Concluding comments :

We have successfully prepared and characterized the bromodioxotriphenylphosphineoxide(N,N' -dialkyldithiocarbamate)molybdenum(VI) complexes, $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$ ($\text{NR}_2 = \text{NEt}_2, \text{N}(i\text{-Pr})_2, \text{NCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)\text{CH}_2$) and bromodioxo-triphenylphosphineoxide(O -alkyldithiocarbonate)molybdenum(VI) complexes, $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COR})(\text{OPPh}_3)$ ($\text{R} = \text{Et}, n\text{-Pr}, i\text{-Pr}$). Although it is quite difficult to comment on the structures of the complexes $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{L})(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)]$ and $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{L})(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ ($\text{L} = \text{OPPh}_3$) in the absence of an X-ray crystal structure of at least one of the products, the tentative structures in Fig. 2 may be proposed on the basis of the above studies.

Fig. 2. Proposed structures of $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{OPPh}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{CNR}_2)]$ (a) and $[\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{OPPh}_3)(\text{S}_2\text{COR})]$ (b) [$\text{NR}_2 = \text{NEt}_2, \text{N}(i\text{-Pr})_2, \text{NCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2$]; $\text{R}' = \text{Et}, n\text{-Pr}, i\text{-Pr}$].

Experimental

All synthetic work was carried out under strictly anhydrous conditions. $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and triphenylphosphineoxide were procured commercially from E. Merck. All solvents (methanol, ethanol, isopropanol, dichloromethane, *n*-hexane and benzene) were dried by standard methods before use. Literature methods were used for the preparation of sodium or potassium salts of *N,N*-dialkyl dithiocarbamates¹⁹ and *O*-alkyldithiocarbonates²⁰.

Synthesis of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (1), $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-Pr})_2\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (2) and $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CNCH}_2(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (3) :

Typically, a suspension of $\text{NaS}_2\text{CNEt}_2$ (0.105 g, 0.613 mmol) in dichloromethane was added to a solution of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}_2(\text{OPPh}_3)_2$ (0.51 g, 0.604 mmol) in dichloromethane in equimolar ratio with constant stirring. The pale yellow solution immediately turned bright yellow. After stirring for 3 h, the precipitated NaBr was filtered and washed with CH_2Cl_2 . Excess solvent was removed, and then the product was dried *in vacuo* and purified by repeated washings with dried benzene to give $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{CNEt}_2)(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (1). Yellow powdery solid. Yield : 0.30 g, 78%; m.p. 98 °C (Found : Mo, 15.36; S, 10.35; Br, 12.29. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{23}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_3\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 15.12; S, 10.11, Br, 12.60%).

Method as above gave $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CN}(i\text{-Pr})_2\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (2). Pale yellow powdery solid. Yield : 82%; m.p. 102 °C (Found : Mo, 14.71; S, 9.81; Br, 12.22. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{25}\text{H}_{29}\text{NO}_3\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 14.48; S, 9.68; Br, 12.06%). Method as above gave $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CNCH}_2$

$(\text{CH}_2)_3\text{CH}_2\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (3). Pale yellow powdery solid. Yield : 86%; m.p. 88 °C (Found : Mo, 15.06; S, 9.77; Br, 12.48. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{24}\text{H}_{25}\text{NO}_3\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 14.84; S, 9.92; Br, 12.36%).

Synthesis of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COEt})(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (4), $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{O}(n\text{-Pr})\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (5) and $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CO}(i\text{-Pr})\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (6) :

A suspension of NaS_2COEt (0.082 g, 0.567 mmol) in dichloromethane was added to a solution of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}_2(\text{OPPh}_3)_2$ (0.48 g, 0.568 mmol) in dichloromethane in equimolar ratio with constant stirring. The pale yellow solution immediately turned bright yellow. After stirring for 3 h, the precipitated NaBr was filtered and washed with dichloromethane. Excess solvent was removed and the product was dried *in vacuo*, and then purified by repeated washing with dried benzene to give $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}(\text{S}_2\text{COEt})(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (4). Yellow solid. Yield : 0.28 g, 81%; m.p. 94 °C (Found : Mo, 15.90; S, 10.83; Br, 13.33. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_4\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 15.80; S, 10.56; Br, 13.16%).

Method as above gave $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CO}(n\text{-Pr})\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (5). Pale yellow solid. Yield : 81%; m.p. 95 °C (Found : Mo, 15.71; S, 10.36; Br, 13.03. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 15.44; S, 10.32; Br, 12.86%). Method as above gave $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}\{\text{S}_2\text{CO}(i\text{-Pr})\}(\text{OPPh}_3)$ (6). Pale yellow solid. Yield : 85%; m.p. 90 °C (Found : Mo, 15.69; S, 10.44; Br, 12.64. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_4\text{PS}_2\text{BrMo}$: Mo, 15.44; S, 10.32; Br, 12.86%).

Attempted synthesis of $\text{MoO}_2\text{Br}_2(\text{CMeCHCHCMeCHN})_2$:

Concentrated HBr (5 ml) was added to a solution of $\text{Na}_2\text{MoO}_4 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.51 g, 2.11 mmol) in distilled water (5 ml). A pale yellow solution along with a significant amount of crystallized NaBr was formed on stirring the mixture for 25–30 min. Diethyl ether (10 ml) was added, the solution was shaken vigorously, and the upper layer was collected. The extraction process was repeated twice more. The combined ether extract was stirred with anhydrous magnesium sulphate for 2 h and then filtered and washed with ether. A white precipitate was immediately observed when an ethanolic solution of CMeCHCHCMeCHN (0.23 g, 2.15 mmol) was added dropwise to a stirred solution of the ether extract. The mixture was stirred for 30 min and filtered, washed with ether and dried under vacuum to give $[\text{CMeCHCHCMeCHNH}]\text{Br}$. White solid. Yield : 86%; m.p. 88 °C (Found : Br, 42.92. Calcd. for $\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{N}_1\text{Br}$: Br, 42.49%). Colourless crystals were obtained on refrigerated overnight *n*-hexane layered dichloromethane solution of the compound.

Physical measurements :

Molybdenum was estimated by precipitation as molybdenum oxinate, $\text{MoO}_2(\text{C}_9\text{H}_6\text{ON})_2$. Sulphur was estimated gravimetrically as barium sulphate [Messenger's method] and bromide volumetrically by Volhard's method. IR spectra ($4000\text{--}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded on an ABBomen FTLA-2000 spectrophotometer using KBr discs. ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker DRX-300 spectrometer in CDCl_3 using TMS as an internal standard.

X-Ray diffraction analysis :

A colourless block crystal of 2,5-dimethylpyridium bromide was mounted on a glass fibre. Data was collected on a Bruker-Nonius Kappa CCD area detector diffractometer, with ϕ and ω scans chosen to give a complete asymmetric unit. Cell refinement²⁹ gave cell constants corresponding to a monoclinic cell whose dimen-

sions are given in Table 3 along with other experimental parameters. An absorption correction was applied³⁰.

The structure was solved by direct method³¹ and was refined using the WinGX version³² of SHELX-97³³. All of the non-hydrogen atoms were treated anisotropically. Hydrogen atoms were located in the difference map and refined isotropically. The final cycle of full-matrix least-squares refinement was based on 1867 observed reflections (1620 for $F^2 > 4\sigma(F^2)$) and 122 variable parameters and converged (largest parameter shift was 0.001 times its esd).

Distances and bond angles are given in Table 4 and the molecule is displayed as an ORTEP diagram in Fig. 1.

Table 3. Crystal data and structure refinement for 2,5-dimethylpyridiumbromide

Empirical formula	$\text{C}_7\text{H}_{10}\text{NBr}$
Formula weight	188.07
Temperature (K)	120(2)
Wavelength (Å)	0.71073
Crystal system	Monoclinic
Space group	$P2_1/c$
<i>A</i> (Å)	8.6591(9)
<i>B</i> (Å)	13.252(1)
<i>C</i> (Å)	7.258(1)
β (°)	101.94(1)
Volume (Å ³)	814.9(2)
<i>Z</i>	4
Density (calculated) (g/cm ³)	1.533
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	4.961
<i>F</i> (000)	376
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.08 × 0.08 × 0.07
θ range for data collection (°)	3.07 to 27.62
Index ranges	$-11 \leq h \leq 10, -17 \leq k \leq 17, -9 \leq l \leq 8$
Reflections collected	10793
Independent reflections	1867 [$R_{\text{int}} = 0.0509$]
Max. and min. transmission	0.7227 and 0.6923
Refinement method	Full-matrix least-squares on F^2
Data/restraints/parameters	1867/0/122
Goodness-of-fit on F^2	1.057
Final <i>R</i> indices [$F^2 > 4\sigma(F^2)$]	$R_1 = 0.0393, wR_2 = 0.0885$
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	$R_1 = 0.0471, wR_2 = 0.0922$
Largest diff. peak and hole (e.Å ⁻³)	2.266 and -0.647

Table 4. Bond lengths (Å) and angles (°) for 2,5-dimethylpyridiumbromide

N(1)–C(1)	1.341(5)	N(1)–C(5)	1.355(5)
C(1)–C(2)	1.389(5)	C(2)–C(3)	1.383(5)
C(3)–C(4)	1.396(6)	C(4)–C(5)	1.381(5)
C(1)–C(6)	1.500(5)	C(4)–C(7)	1.501(5)
N(1)–H(1)	0.81(5)	H(1)–Br(1)	2.38(5)
N(1)–Br(1)	3.183(3)		
C(1)–N(1)–C(5)	123.8(3)	N(1)–C(1)–C(6)	118.1(3)
N(1)–C(1)–C(2)	117.3(3)	C(2)–C(1)–C(6)	124.6(3)
C(1)–C(2)–C(3)	120.3(4)	C(2)–C(3)–C(4)	121.2(3)
C(3)–C(4)–C(5)	116.7(3)	C(3)–C(4)–C(7)	122.2(3)
C(5)–C(4)–C(7)	121.1(4)	N(1)–C(5)–C(4)	120.6(4)
C(1)–N(1)–H(1)	121(3)	C(5)–N(1)–H(1)	115(3)
N(1)–H(1)–Br(1)	179(4)		

CCDC 678918 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for [CMeCHCHCMeCHNH]Br. This can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 2EZ, UK (Fax : +44 1223 336033); E-mail : deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Acknowledgement

Two of us (RK and RR) are grateful to UGC, New Delhi for financial support. KS thanks the DST, New Delhi for financial support. MBH thanks the UK Engineering and Physical Sciences Council for support of the X-ray facilities at Southampton University. JED wishes to thank the University of Windsor for financial support. We are also thankful to RSIC, CDRI, Lucknow for the NMR spectral analyses.

References

1. R. C. Bray and J. C. Swann, *Structure and Bonding*, 1972, **11**, 107.
2. J. T. Spence, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1969, **4**, 475.
3. R. A. D. Wentworth, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1976, **18**, 1.
4. R. J. Butcher, H. P. Guntz, R. G. A. R. Maclagon, H. K. J. Powell, C. J. Wilkins and S. H. Yong, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1975, 1223.
5. R. J. Butcher, H. K. J. Powell, C. J. Wilkins and S. H. Yong, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1976, 356.
6. R. J. Butcher and B. R. Penfold, *J. Cryst. Mol. Struct.*, 1976, **6**, 1.
7. R. J. Butcher and B. R. Penfold, *J. Cryst. Mol. Struct.*, 1976, **6**, 13.
8. R. J. Butcher, B. R. Penfold and E. Slim, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1979, 668.
9. N. Manwani, M. C. Gupta, R. Ratnani, J. E. Drake, M. B. Hursthouse and M. E. Light, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2004, **357**, 939.
10. A. L. Bingham, J. E. Drake, M. B. Hursthouse, M. E. Light, R. Kumar and R. Ratnani, *Polyhedron*, 2006, **25**, 3238.
11. F. J. Arnaiz, R. Aguado, M. R. Pedrosa and A. De Cian, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2003, **347**, 33.
12. R. Ratnani, M. F. Davis, W. Levason, M. Webster, G. Reid and T. Rose, *Eur. J. Inorg. Chem.*, 2007, 306.
13. R. H. Holm, *Chem. Rev.*, 1987, **87**, 1401.
14. M. L. Mader, M. D. Carducci and J. H. Enemark, *Inorg. Chem.*, 2000, **39**, 525.
15. F. J. Arnaiz, R. Aguado and J. M. Martinez Harduya, *Polyhedron*, 1994, **13**, 3257.
16. E. J. Stiefel, *Prog. Inorg. Chem.*, 1977, **22**, 1.
17. E. J. Stiefel, W. E. Newton, G. D. Watt, K. L. Hadfield and W. A. Bulen, *Advance Chem. Ser.*, 1977, **162**, 353.
18. R. Ratnani, M. B. Hursthouse, W. Levason and G. Reid, *Polyhedron*, 2004, **23**, 1915.
19. H. L. Klopping and G. J. M. Van der Kerk, *Res. Trav. Chim.*, 1951, **70**, 919.
20. R. J. Magee and M. J. O'Connor, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1971, **5**, 554.
21. R. N. Jowitt and P. C. H. Mitchell, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1970, 1702.
22. G. S. Bhat and A. D. Sawant, *Thermochim. Acta*, 1993, **222**, 231.
23. F. J. Arnaiz, R. Aguado, M. R. Pedrosa, A. De Cian and J. Fisher, *Polyhedron*, 2000, **19**, 2141.
24. P. Nag, R. Bohra, R. C. Mehrotra and R. Ratnani, *Synth. React. Inorg. Metal-Org. Chem.*, 2002, **32**, 1549.
25. H. Ishida and S. Kashino, *Z. Naturforsch., A. Phys. Sci.*, 2002, **57**, 829.
26. B. F. Ali and R. Al-Far, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 2007, **C63**, m451.
27. C. Bannister, K. Burns, K. Prout and D. J. Watkin, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1994, **B50**, 221.
28. A. Luque, J. Sertucha, L. Lezama, T. Rojo and P. Roman, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 1997, 847.
29. A. J. M. Duisenberg *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 1992, **25**, 92.
30. G. M. Sheldrick, *SADABS V2.10*, 2003.
31. G. M. Sheldrick, *Acta Crystallogr.*, 1990, **A46**, 467.
32. L. J. Farrugia, *J. Appl. Cryst.*, 1999, **32**, 837.
33. G. M. Sheldrick, *SHELXL97* (University of Gottingen, Germany).